

Some Applications of Magnetic Resonance of Water Protons in Chemistry

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The relaxivity—due to Fe^{III} moieties—in the solutions of the complex $[\text{H Fe}^{\text{III}} \text{EDTA}, \text{H}_2\text{O}]$ was measured to be approximately 1/5th of that in the solutions of $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}, 6\text{H}_2\text{O}]$. Changes in the spin-lattice (T_1) relaxation times of water protons in a sample of the solution containing Fe^{III} , Mn^{II} , Ni^{II} or VO^{II} ions established the extent of hydrolysis during the experimental period. Surface reactions in the sample tube, which was made of a kind of sodalime glass, slowly increased the pH of its content. When appropriate increase in the pH was induced in a sample of the VO^{II} ions, transient shortenings of the spin-spin (T_2) relaxation times were noted. That phenomena was followed by the anticipated increases in the subsequent T_2 s due to the consequent hydrolyses of some of the VO^{II} ions. Detectable formation of silicatoferri complex, during storage of solutions of ferric chloride, in the experimental sample tube was envisaged.

The micro-pulse magnetic resonance spectrometer¹ has been useful in some investigations related to paramagnetic relaxations of water protons². Paramagnetic ions decrease both T_1 and T_2 of the corresponding solutions.

When Fe^{III} ions were complexed³ with ethylenediamine tetraacetic acid (EDTA), however, the T_1 s of the resulting solutions were observed to increase.

If the relative concentration of the paramagnetic component in an experimental solution is decreased, both T_1 and T_2 of that sample are expected to increase. For example, when the paramagnetic components either precipitate out of the experimental solution or change to diamagnetic moieties during their hydrolyses, the relative concentration of the paramagnetic ions decreases in the sample. Thus T_1 s have been observed to increase (Fig. 2) during the hydrolyses of the Fe^{III} ions in a sample of ferric nitrate solution. Similarly, the monitored increases of the respective T_1 s (Fig. 3 : a, b and c) corresponding to the samples of solutions of Mn^{II} , VO^{II} and Ni^{II} , described different aspects of their hydrolysis courses. When the pH of

a solution of VO^{II} was momentarily increased from 3.6 to nearly 4.4, a transient decrease in T_2 s (Fig. 4) was noted. The anticipated increases in T_2 s due to initiation of the process of hydrolysis, followed that phenomenon.

A comparison of the concentration curves due to Fe^{III} ions in nine samples of ferric chloride solutions indicated of detectable increases in the monitored T_1 s after storage of the samples in the experimental glass tubes. Such increases in the respective T_1 s are rationalised by considering losses of the corresponding amounts of the Fe^{III} ions during the storage.

The chemical composition of the experimental glass tubes (103×10.2 mm) included $\approx 16\%$ sodium, 1.4% calcium, lesser proportions of aluminium and magnesium, and trace amounts of copper, iron, manganese and zinc. While it also contained significant proportion of boron, silicon and oxygen together constituted almost all of the rest of this glass composition.

It was primarily the reaction of the alkali metal oxide of the glass surface⁴ with the contained solution, that slowly raised its pH with time.

When dilute hydrochloric acid (pH \approx 4.2) was kept in such glass tubes, the pH was observed to rise from \approx 5.8 to 6.2 (Fig. 5) during the period of 28 days (4th to 32nd).

Results and Discussion

The concentration curve (Fig. 1b) of [H Fe^{III} EDTA, H₂O] is a typical representation of paramagnetic relaxation. As the concentration of the Fe^{III} moieties in the experimental samples increased, the *T*₁s correspondingly decreased and vice versa. Similarly, the respective concentrations of the Fe^{III} ions in the experimental ferric chloride solutions are related to the reported *T*₁s in Fig. 1a.

Fig. 1. Plots of *T*₁ (milliseconds) vs Fe^{III} concentration (mg dl⁻¹) (□) FeCl₃ solutions and (O) [HFe^{III} EDTA, H₂O] solutions.

A region of the continued progress of hydrolysis of Fe^{III} ions in a sample of ferric nitrate solution, corresponded to Fig. 2. It was between the pH of 2.7 and 2.9 and at 29°. As the concentration of the Fe^{III} ions decreased, the *T*₁s increased correspondingly.

Fig. 2. Fe(NO₃)₃ solutions in the (O) sample tube, and (□) prepared solution at 29°; *T*₁ in milliseconds.

Fig. 3. Chemical changes corresponded to (□) MnCl₂ solution, (Δ) VOSO₄ solution, and (O) NiCl₂ solution; *T*₁ in milliseconds.

Fig. 3 describes different aspects of the respective hydrolyses of Mn^{II} , VO^{II} and Ni^{II} ions in the samples of the corresponding solutions at room temperature. As the concentration of the paramagnetic ions decreased, the $T1$ s increased accordingly.

When the pH of a sample of the VO^{II} solution was momentarily raised from 3.6 to just above 4 at $\approx 29^\circ$, however, a transient decrease in the monitored $T2$ s was noted (Fig. 4) before the anticipated rises in the $T2$ s due to the subsequent hydrolyses of some of the VO^{II} ions.

Fig. 4. Alkali induced chemical changes in a sample of $VOSO_4$ solution; $T2$ in milliseconds.

The $T1$ s of the samples of solutions of nine different concentrations of ferric chloride were measured. Those solutions were stored at room temperature in the experimental glass tubes for 91 days. Very small but detectable increases in the respective $T1$ s were noted after the period of storage.

When different volumes of samples of dilute hydrochloric acid solution of pH 2.1 were stored in six experimental glass tubes, no change in pH, in the contents of any of those tubes, was detected after 189 days of storage at room temperature. The respective pHs of a very dilute solution, however, increased (Fig. 5) from ≈ 5.8 on the 4th day to ≈ 6.2 on the 32nd in four experimental tubes.

Fig. 5. Neutralisations of very dilute hydrochloric acid : (O) 1.5 ml, (□) 2 ml, (Δ) 2.5 ml and (●) 3 ml during the respective storages in the experimental glass tubes.

While the observed decrease in relaxivity (Fig. 1 : a,b) is rationalised by considering the reduction of the number of H_2O molecules in the first coordination sphere from 6 in $[Fe^{III}, 6H_2O]$ to 1 in the complex $[H Fe^{III} EDTA, H_2O]$, it is tempting to consider another outlook. Five unpaired electrons are supposed to exist in the $3d$ orbitals of the metal in the electrostatic or ionic⁵ complex $[Fe^{III}, 6H_2O]$. Considering d^2sp^3 hybridised linkages in the complex $[H Fe^{III} EDTA, H_2O]$, only one unpaired electron appears to

be in the $3d$ orbitals of the Fe^{III} moiety. Since paramagnetic relaxation relates to unpaired electrons in the relevant metal ions, this reduction in the number from 5 in the ionic complex $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}, 6\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ to 1 in $[\text{H Fe}^{\text{III}} \text{EDTA}, \text{H}_2\text{O}]$ complex may be the cause of the observed decrease in relaxivity (Fig. 1 : a,b).

While the initial pH of the continued hydrolysis of Fe^{III} ions (Fig. 2) in a sample of ferric nitrate solution, was 2.7, that after the experimental period was measured to be 2.9. The pH of the original solution, also maintained at 29° , however, went down to 2.6 at the end of that period. The observed higher pH of the sample was considered to be the consequence of surface reactions with the sample tube.

Such surface reactions made the complete hydrolysis in a sample of Mn^{II} ions (Fig. 3a) possible. The pH of the original solution was less than 6 (≈ 5.6). Other experiments indicated such hydrolyses at $\text{pH} \approx 7.6$.

A period during the hydrolyses of VO^{II} ions in one of those experimental tubes is described in Fig. 3b. The resulting decreases in the paramagnetic relaxations were related to the observed increases in the corresponding T_1 s. Colour changes⁶ in this case also provided less precise indications of the chemical change. In other words, the colour of the yet unhydrolysed sample was blue. That of a completely hydrolysed one was very pale yellow. It contained dark brown precipitate in it. The progress of the hydrolysis corresponded to the colour changes of the supernatant from bluish green, greenish blue, green, yellowish green, greenish yellow, and finally very pale straw-yellow.

The initiation of hydrolyses of the Ni^{II} ions at $\text{pH} \approx 6$ in an experimental sample tube, is illustrated in Fig. 3c. Continued hydrolyses were noted in other samples at pH 6.1 and also 6.4.

As the pH was increased from 3.6 to just above 4 in a sample of VO^{II} ions, consecutive

T_2 measurements indicated an initial decrease in T_2 . A very slight increase in the temperature may have been caused by the released heat from the acid-base reaction :

That temperature rise in its turn brought about the transient decrease⁷ in T_2 (Fig. 4). Such T_2 enhancement is now considered to be primarily due to the proportionate increase in the hydrogen bondings at the region of the outer (i.e. 3rd) sphere of H_2O molecules around each VO^{II} ion.

When samples of different concentrations of ferric chloride solutions ($\text{pH} \approx 1.8$) were stored in the experimental glass tubes for 91 days, small but detectable increases in their respective T_1 s were noted. In order to rationalise such an increase in T_1 , loss of the corresponding amount of Fe^{III} ions was envisaged. While possible hydrolyses to correspond to the decrease in relaxivity, were not ruled out, reactions with the glass surface of the sample tube to form the complexes like $-\text{SiOFe}^{2+}$ were also considered.

Storage of 4 different volumes of very dilute hydrochloric acid ($\text{pH} \approx 4.2$) in the corresponding experimental tubes, indicated significant rises in the respective pHs (Fig. 5). Such an increase in pH was considered to be primarily due to neutralisations of the corresponding proportion of $(\text{H}_3\text{O})^+$ ions after their reactions with the equivalent amount of NaO-moieties existing on the inside surface of the experimental glass tube. Considering no detectable change in the pH of 2.1 after storage in such tubes, it became apparent that the existing amount of NaO- on the inside surface of such a tube was not enough for the latter purpose.

Experimental

A Seimco micropulse magnetic resonance spectrometer (New Kensington, Pennsylvania, U.S.A.) was used for the determination of the

reported T_1 and T_2 . At 13.2 MHz and 29°, T_1 of a sample of deionised water was \approx 3 000 milliseconds. At the time of the reported experiments, T_2 of that sample approximated 2000 milliseconds.

The T_1 determinations corresponded to computer-programming of Freeman-Hill saturation recovery methods⁸. T_2 measurements were programmed according to the Meiboom and Gill⁹ modifications of Carr-Purcell¹⁰ method.

All of the pH measurements were made in a Fisher-Accumet 900 pH meter. While exploratory works were done with a liquid-filled, glass-body, combination electrode with silver/silver chloride reference, much of the reported work corresponded to the measurements with a calomel electrode (Fisher). The pH meter was adjusted to pH 4 with an appropriately dilute buffer solution from the concentrate SB-99-500 (Fisher). Similarly, the concentrate SB-109-500 (Fisher) after proper dilution, provided the standard buffer for pH 7 adjustments.

While most of the fine chemicals including the reagent grade hydrochloric acid solution, were purchased from reputed chemical companies, a purer sample of vanadyl sulphate was kindly donated by the then director of the laboratory. That sample was used in the reported T_2 measurements.

Experimental solutions of the complex, [H Fe^{III} EDTA, H₂O], were prepared from the following solutions of known concentrations : (a) Na₂ EDTA, 2H₂O was dissolved in boiled and cooled deionised water, and (b) a dilute ferric

chloride solution was further diluted. A measured volume of solution (a) was added to a measured volume of solution (b) to yield each experimental solution of the described complex. While pH of the resulting solutions ranged between 1.9 and 3.5, the proportion of EDTA, in comparison to the amount of Fe^{III}, in each, was more than 1.8 molar equivalents. Since the colour of the reactant dilute ferric chloride solution was not always visually perceptible, it was the development of the characteristic yellow colour rather than the intensification of it, indicated the formation of the complex [H Fe^{III} EDTA, H₂O]. A striking decrease in the relaxivity, as was exhibited by the higher T_1 in each sample, confirmed the existence of the complex.

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References

1. H. C. TORREY, *Phys. Rev.*, 1949, **75**, 1326.
2. R. C. CONGER and P. W. SELWOOD, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1952, **20**, 383.
3. W. KLEMM, *Z. Anorg. Chem.*, 1944, **252**, 225.
4. H. H. DUNKEN, *Silikaty*, 1987, **31**, 151.
5. E. C. SCOTT and F. A. KANDA, "The Nature of Atoms and Molecules : A General Chemistry", Harper & Row, New York, 1962, p. 505.
6. H. T. S. BRITTON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1842.
7. R. HAUSSER and G. LAUKIEN, *Z. Phys.*, 1959, **153**, 394.
8. R. FREEMAN and H. D. W. HILL, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1971, **54**, 3367.
9. S. MEIBOOM and D. GILL, *Rev. Sci. Instr.*, 1958, **29**, 688.
10. H. Y. CARR and E. M. PURCELL, *Phys. Rev.*, 1954, **94**, 630.

